

IMPORTANCE OF GENDER IN EDUCATION

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Annotation: *In recent years, the relevance of the problem of gender equality has been increasing in Uzbekistan. A comprehensive solution to the problem includes the sphere of education, the educational process, the content of textbooks and other educational materials. Improving the gender content of education is based on the provisions of gender pedagogy.*

Key words: *women, men, gender inequality, gender pedagogy, international cooperation, gender, gender approach, gender theory, gender pedagogy.*

In the 20th and 21st centuries, the world is undergoing a process of revision and practical change in the stereotypes of gender-role identification of society. The main direction of the ongoing changes lies in a new look at the place and role of women in various areas of labor and social activity, at the idea of a harmonious combination of motives, interests, positions and activities of both sexes. Many researchers note and cite the growing role of women in various fields of activity - in public administration, in science, medicine, education, culture and art. [4,5].

In research L. S. Rykova, M.M. Malysheva rightly notes that the female part of the population makes a great contribution to the functioning and improvement of the quality of labor resources. [6,7].

It is indicated that the economically active population of most developed industrial countries are women (indicators are at the level of 40% to 50%.) The professional activity of women, as studies show, has a significant impact on the growth of the national income of the leading countries of the world, largely changing the models of interaction in the professional environment and defining many directions of social paradigms of human development [7,8].

In Uzbekistan, over the past two years, there has been an intensification of activities to eliminate gender inequality. The problems of gender policy, gender studies, especially in relation to the "women's issue" are classified at the official level among the priority issues of state policy.

Measures have been taken to improve the status of women, especially in terms of protecting and expanding their rights through legislative documents. In 2019, before Uzbekistan submitted its sixth periodic report to the UN CEDAW Committee (Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women), two laws were adopted: "On the Protection of Women from Harassment and Violence"[1] and "On Guarantees of Equal Rights and opportunities for women and men"[2].

At the beginning of 2020, the Women's Committee of Uzbekistan was abolished as a structure under the Cabinet of Ministers, designed to be responsible for virtually all problems in the social, labor, family and cultural life of women. At the same time, the functions of the Women's Committee of Uzbekistan were distributed between the new Ministry for the Support of Mahalla and Family and structures under the Senate of Uzbekistan - the Committee on Women and Gender Equality and the Commission on Ensuring Gender Equality of the Republic of Uzbekistan. In parallel, the mahalla, as a self-governing body, was given the rank of the Ministry.

Currently, mahalla is the main body of self-government of citizens in such important areas as:

- distribution of social payments to women;
- implementation of the system of "Women's Notebooks" for the allocation of loans and one-time material assistance to women from socially vulnerable segments of the population.

In May 2021, the Strategy for achieving gender equality in Uzbekistan until 2030 was adopted. This document provides for the creation of departments for gender equality in each ministry and department, which requires the training of personnel - employees of such departments, the development and implementation of mechanisms for achieving the goal.

Among the obvious positive changes is the more effective cooperation of state structures with international organizations and NGOs - non-governmental non-profit. International cooperation allows conducting a comparative analysis, making critical recommendations, adopting positive experience, adopting and implementing relevant legal documents, achieving world standards, choosing the most appropriate and effective forms of activity for leveling gender equality for the conditions of Uzbekistan. Such cooperation certainly contributes to the development, improvement and implementation of standard operating procedures for the prevention of violence against women, which should be adopted in the near future.

However, as Webster University Associate Professor Nozima Davletova points out, "...a number of systemic challenges remain that will, in the long run, hinder the achievement of tangible results in the field of empowerment of women and girls in the country, as well as the reduction of gender-based violence." [3p.3].

The inclusion of gender theory and tools of gender analysis in the educational process of primary, secondary and higher schools and the training of qualified educators is extremely relevant today. The level of gender culture of education system employees determines how children and students will be brought up in educational institutions: in the spirit of traditional sexism or taking into account gender balance [6].

"Sexism is an attitude or action that belittles, excludes, underestimates and stereotypes people based on their gender. Sexism is an orientation that disadvantages one sex in relation to the other." Along with feminized pedagogy, these trends complicate the process of socialization, both for boys and girls. High demands on boys, indicated in stereotypes, can lead to stress, illness if they do not meet the accepted standard. And girls are still forced to break, suppress natural inclinations, to refuse full-fledged, free mental and intellectual development [10].

The most complex gender system is the pedagogical one. Author N.Yu. Erofeeva aptly notes that we are talking about a system of relations that is built mainly by women (given the presence of their quantitative majority in pedagogical activity). However, the specifics of the profession require them to perform different gender roles (teacher, class teacher, methodologist, leader, teacher - all masculine?) and, accordingly, the presence of qualities inherent in both men and women.

It is clear that not all female teachers are capable of this. Meanwhile, as statistics show, it is girls who achieve greater success in their studies than boys. Perhaps this is because teaching methods are based on the transmission of information (feminine), and not on experimental and research activities (masculine) [8].

The term "gender" was introduced into science in order to distinguish between the biological and social characteristics of sex (translated from English gender - "genus"). The concept of "gender" reflects the social nature of male and female and draws attention to the fact that social differences between men and women are not always a natural continuation of biological differences, but are due to the influence of external factors. Scientist M.L. Spirina defines "gender" as a specific set of cultural and

behavioral characteristics that determine the social behavior of men and women[9].

According to E.K. Vasilyeva, "gender" is a social gender, socially determined roles, identities and spheres of activity of men and women, which depend not on biological sex differences, but on the social organization of society[11].

The concept of "gender pedagogy" is used in pedagogical theory and practice relatively recently. Gender pedagogy is a branch of pedagogy that studies the features of gender socialization, education and upbringing of boys and girls.

Gender pedagogy is a new developing branch of pedagogical knowledge, therefore, until now, its conceptual apparatus is in the process of formation. Many concepts used by gender pedagogy do not have an unambiguous interpretation in pedagogical theory.

The importance of gender pedagogy in solving the problems of personality formation, in improving the educational process is due to a number of factors.

In children, sexual (gender) roles do not exist in a ready-made, adult form, but are formed in the course of socialization. "Men and women in the social sense are not born, they become as a result of purposeful education, which is important to start as early as possible, already from preschool age" [12 p. 5].

As practice has shown, "asexual pedagogy", which does not take into account the psychological characteristics of boys and girls, is unable to effectively solve the problems of gender-based socialization of the younger generation, preparing to fulfill gender social roles.

The gender approach in education, i.e. taking into account gender psychological differences (psychophysiological, personal), makes it possible to ensure greater efficiency in the processes of education, upbringing, and personality formation.

According to A.V. Mudrik, the use of knowledge about gender characteristics is necessary in organizing the life and activities of educational organizations; in determining the content and methods of teaching; in creating conditions for boys and girls to master the norms, models, scenarios and experience of gender-role behavior, adequate to their age status, development, social expectations.

The main tasks of gender pedagogy are:

- development of theoretical foundations, concepts of gender education;

- development of programs and technologies for upbringing and education, taking into account the gender differences of children [13].

The gender approach in pedagogy involves the use of knowledge about the gender characteristics of representatives of different sexes in the process of education and training and is implemented in two main directions:

- creation of conditions for gender socialization, mastering by children of models of sex-role behavior adequate to age, preparation for the performance of sexual (gender roles) in the future;

- application of gender-oriented technologies of education and upbringing.

Gender pedagogy is an actively developing branch of scientific pedagogical knowledge. The implementation of the gender approach in education meets the urgent requirements of the time, the trends in the development of scientific theory and the demands of pedagogical practice.

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